

Wann wird die erste KI die New York Times-Bestsellerliste anführen?

11 August 2021

Eine Untersuchung sprachgenerierender Algorithmen und ihrer Auswirkungen auf die Gesellschaft

Language generators based on artificial intelligence are producing increasingly convincing texts. This led us to wonder: Could an AI guest-author an article in *Encore*? The AI-written text you will see below is the result of our experiment. This is what we did: the first paragraph is a human-written prompt. It is based on the introduction to HIIG researcher Alexander Pirang's blog post *Is the COVID-19 pandemic social media platforms' chance at redemption?* published on the Digital Society Blog in April 2020. The prompt was fed to InferKit, which offers an accessible version of the language model GPT-2. Released by OpenAI in 2019, this language model generates articles, poems or even code based on minimal prompts.

Does the result convince you? To keep things raw and provide a better idea of how the technology works, the AI-written piece below remains fully unedited. Finally, three HIIG researchers discuss the results and the potential impact of recently developed language-generating technologies.

The result

Human-written prompt: Is the COVID-19 pandemic social media platforms' chance at redemption? Faced with an *infodemic* in the wake of COVID-19, social media platforms have ramped up their efforts to address misinformation. Facebook in particular seems to have implemented a surprisingly robust coronavirus response. These efforts could reinforce a public value-driven approach to content governance, but they could also be problems posing as solutions.

AI-written output: As social media platforms monitor users' interactions, can they track and manage extremist content more effectively? This requires greater transparency, transparency that has so far been lacking. We are seeing much more transparency today, but most of it is being framed through terms that have been harnessed by proponents of transparency, making it difficult for third parties to understand.

Prior to COVID-19, Facebook (NASDAQ: FB) had faced concern about the quality and impact of their news feed. Users who wanted to stay informed were not being exposed to high quality, trustworthy content. Following COVID-19, there has been intense media scrutiny on Facebook, which may further influence its users to actively seek out reliable news sources. Whatever changes Facebook implements, how effective will they be? Based

on the problems Facebook has had with extremism on its platform, can it really be trusted to make these changes?

In a similar vein, Twitter has arguably already faced unprecedented levels of scrutiny for its role in monitoring and policing the content on its platform. Twitter's role in monitoring content, in contrast to Facebook's, has focused more on fear-mongering and inflammatory commentary that has given rise to a series of debates over what constitutes a hate-filled tweet and who is ultimately responsible for the content posted on Twitter.

Facebook's role in supporting the election of Donald Trump has created an environment of mistrust between the social media company and its users. While a majority of people who liked Donald Trump on Facebook have affirmed that their decision was based on his platform, which in turn led to the popularisation of the term "Trump Truther", how effective can Facebook be in correcting the damage of its recent election support and how will it manage those who have made a poor choice?

It is important that Twitter continues to show leadership by removing the offensive tweets and deactivating the accounts that were created as a result of the election of Donald Trump. The removal of the offending tweets and support for the ban of Milo Yiannopoulos should signal that Twitter will resist attempts to influence users' choices with hate speech and that it will do all it can to support free speech.

The context

HIIG researchers Shlomi Hod, Alexander Pirang and Frédéric Dubois were asked to provide perspectives from their fields of expertise on the article written by the AI guest author. Shlomi is a visiting researcher at HIIG's AI & Society Lab and computer science PhD candidate at Boston University. Alexander is a researcher at HIIG, currently writing his doctoral thesis on the implications of platform governance for users' right to freedom of expression. Frédéric is managing editor of HIIG's Internet Policy Review and PhD candidate at the Film University Babelsberg. The interview was conducted by Sonja Köhne.

Read the interview [here](#).

Dieser Text wurde zuerst in unserem Forschungsmagazin [encore](#) veröffentlicht.